

AN ARCHITECTURE OF NUMBERS RAISED TO A POWER

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Fermat's Last Theorem is the same as saying the difference between two cubes cannot be a cube, and so on with powers greater than 3 and up to infinity. So to start with I looked at cubic numbers from 0 and going up to 125, listing them one above the other like a tower. I then wrote in the differences between those differences and then again between those differences until they reached 0. So it is like a tower collapsing. For example, in the case of numbers raised to the power of 5, you get :-

Fig. 1

125				
	61			
64		24		
	37.		6	
27		18.		0
	19.		6	
8		12.		0
	7.		6	
1		6.		0
	1.		6	
0.		0.		

You can see that all the numbers in the tower collapse to zero. I did this for a few other numbers, raising them to different prime number powers. Of course, because you are only subtracting what you have only just added to zero, you always get back to zero. But the question is, what is the shape of the collapse?

Below is a structure that I designed to investigate exactly how the tower will do that. You are looking for three base numbers, call them a, b and c where a and c are odd. Let us say a is the highest one and you want to raise it to the power of a prime number, p, and then see if you can split that into two smaller numbers, b and c also raised to the power of p. P needs to be a prime or you can't prove anything.

Fig. 2

The number 7, raised to the power of 7, produces the following set of numbers:- 1, 128, 2187, 16384, 78125, 279936, 823543. You can write them in the form of a tower.

I realized that you can think of the tower collapsing in the shape of a cascade, like a waterfall negotiating a craggy cliff. Having done that, I needed another structure, superimposed on the cascade, this one showing the quantities as they separated into smaller quantities and I could see that this one would be based on Pascal's Triangle structure. So I combined the two structures together by printing out the Triangle at a matching scale on a transparent plastic sheet with a set of circles to contain the differences from the table above or some other similar set. In this case it is taken from base number 7 raised to the power of seven. This number is shown in the top left corner as 823543. The circle around it also has connecting tubes with a number in each one. By shifting the transparent Pascal Triangle sheet around you can start it anywhere you like on the cascade and see what happens. Starting from the top the 823543 sends 1 quantity of the number 543607 down to the right, so this tube has a 1 in it. And 1 quantity of 279936 is sent down vertically so that tube also has a 1 in it. If you continue this process you finish up with the structure shown below in Fig.2. If you know the growth triangle (Pascal's Triangle) you will recognise that the numbers in the tubes come from it. The quantity of each number in the collapse is shown by the number in the tube below it.

If you regard this as a collapse downwards, or a deconstruction, you can reverse it to become a construction upwards. So starting from the four bold circles on the zero zone and using the quantities shown immediately below them you get: $7 \times 1 + 56 \times 126 + 126 \times 1680 + 120 \times 5040 = 823543$ which is 7 to the power of 7. I saw these four sets of numbers as four towers which between them were the deconstruction of 7 to the power of 7.

There is no limit to the number of times you can carry out this process. No limit in the base number raised to a power or to that power (which must always, however, be a prime number).

So a structure of this kind can be constructed for each any number raised to any prime exponent greater than two. All the way to infinity. And if you like, you can think of the numbers in the bold circles, all divisible by 6, as two sizes of architectural objects, ones and sixes.

When I saw the group of four results above I saw them as four towers but there was an essential difference. Three results were towers of sixes and one was a tower of ones and they were unique for each base number and for each prime power. If Fermat had seen this would he not have understood its implications immediately? It was clear that you cannot separate the number 823543 into two

smaller numbers also raised to the power of 7 without doing the separations in terms of all four towers. It is a deconstruction and so 6 raised to the power of 7 will also deconstruct in the same manner into four towers of those same numbers but with different multipliers. And for a number raised to the power of 7 the numbers in the bold circles are the same, no matter what the base number is. That is, they are 1, 126, 1680, and 5040. The numbers in the tubes below them are this example, 7, 56, 126, and 120, and they are supplied, as can readily be seen, from the appropriate row and column of the Pascal's Triangle which is the image of the cascade. These multipliers therefore vary according to the base number on the line of the descending shallow diagonal starting with the base number, in this case 7, in the third column of the Triangle. The result of doing this calculation is :- $7 \times 1 + 56 \times 126 + 126 \times 1680 + 120 \times 5040$ which equals 823543, or 7 to the power of 7.

So you can do the same calculation for 6 raised to the power of 7 and it will look like this. $6 \times 1 + 35 \times 126 + 56 \times 1680 + 36 \times 5040 = 279936$, the value of 6 to the power of 7.. So all powers of 7 can be expressed in this way. You can see that no number to the seventh power can be split into any other two numbers to the seventh power because it will fail at the first step, no matter what happens at the other steps of the calculation.

So no matter what the base number is or what the prime exponent is, you are bound to find that the base number multiplier stands alone in its tube multiplying 1 while the other numbers to be multiplied by the numbers in the tubes below them are multiples of six. When you deconstructed 7 to the power of 7 you got three towers made of group of sixes and one tower of seven ones. You cannot use these towers of sixes to construct the towers which are the deconstruction of b and c raised to the power of 7. Even if you find a value for 'a' where the towers of sixes will provide the exact numbers required for 'b' and 'c' it can never do the same for the tower of ones. It will just provide an 'a'. Therefore it is impossible to split base number 'a' raised to the power of 7 into base numbers b and c similarly raised to the power of 7. For an example you can check this in the case of a=16, b=15 and c=9 (which in any case do not meet the initial assumptions)

So three numbers raised to the same power will give different sets of sixes and three base numbers. Whether or not the 'a' set of sixes can be split into the 'b' and 'c' sets, the 'c' set certainly cannot. The inherent architecture of numbers raised to a power prevents it.